

**REVIEW: PRIMARY READINGS IN PHILOSOPHY FOR UNDERSTANDING
THEOLOGY**

By

Prasanna Kumar Monditoka M.Pharm., M.Div.

REVIEW: PRIMARY READINGS IN PHILOSOPHY FOR UNDERSTANDING THEOLOGY

In the book “Primary Readings in Philosophy for Understanding Theology,” Diogenes Allen and Eric O. Springsted collected and organized the primary readings of the philosophers. In this review, some of the key concepts of the philosophers are summarized and analyzed from a theistic perspective.

The Sun, the Line, and the Cave

In the reading “The Sun, the Line, and the Cave,” Plato explained the knowledge of good using an analogy of a conversation between Glaucon and Socrates. Glaucon asked Socrates about the knowledge of good. He asked—what is the actual nature of good? Socrates refused to speak about the actual knowledge of good, but he was willing to talk about “the child of good.” The idea of good is the highest knowledge. The possession of all other things is of no value if the person does not possess “the good.” Plato argued that the cause and source of everything, including science, truth, and beauty, are “the good.” This supreme “good” is the author of knowledge, being, and the essence of all things. However, this “good” far exceeds the essence of nobility and power. The sun gives visibility to all the visible things. He is also the author of all generations, sustenance, and growth. However, he is not the generation. Plato gave an illustration of prisoners in a den to explain his idea of good. The prisoners could see the shadows on the walls, but they do not have access to the outside realities. The soul must ascend to see the realities in the upper intellectual world. Plato argued that only some people achieve this state, and those who achieve this state do not incline to return to normal lower-level human affairs.

Plato acknowledged the realities outside the human realm. Despite his recognition of supreme “good” outside the human realm, his definition of this "good" and his path to ascend to understand it is not in line with the monotheistic Jewish perspective. For Plato, life on earth is

merely a shadow of reality. There is an implied dualism between the shadows in this life and the realities in the upper life. This dichotomy between the lower normal human life and higher intellectual life is distinct from the holistic view of life in the Hebrew Bible. Plato did not acknowledge the philosophical foundations of the theistic views. Though his insistence on achieving a higher intellectual life through education is similar to wisdom literature, he did not acknowledge a covenant God and fear of the Lord. Plato's good is not a personal being, unlike the monotheistic conceptions of transcendent God who is above and beyond the creation (Isaiah 55:8-9) and personal and relational God who is the creator and source of all good (Isaiah 43:3-13, James 1:17, John 1:14, Job 33:4).

Creation

Plato provided an account of nature and means of creation based on philosophical thought, mythological accounts, and natural theology. He attempted to answer the philosophical questions of who created the world and the process of creation. He reasoned that everything that is created must be created by some cause. He acknowledged that there is a god (demiurge), and he brought order out of disorder. By the providence of this god, the world came into existence and became a living creature. The created world is necessarily a corporeal, visible, and tangible world. The body of the universe was created with the elements of fire, earth, air, and water. There are three components in the world, including body, soul, and the intermediate essence. The creator took three components and pressed them. The visible component is the body of heaven. The invisible component is the soul, which partakes of reason and harmony. The only being which has a mind is the soul. The god (demiurge) put intelligence in the soul and the soul in the body (of the universe). He created the world in the image of the eternal gods. When he saw his moving and living creature, he rejoiced in it and made more copies. The time and heaven came into existence at the same instance. The god (demiurge) lighted a fire to give light to heaven and animals. The light is called the sun. He created the sun, moon, and five other stars to distinguish and preserve time. There are four kinds of species: the heavenly race of gods, the race of birds, watery species,

and pedestrian and land creatures. He maintained the otherworldliness of the creator. He argued that it is impossible to speak of the father and creator of the universe.

Plato certainly provided helpful terminology and conceptions to know about the creator and creation. He is right in acknowledging the creator behind the creation and the basic structure of created elements. However, his account of creation is heavily dependent on mythological elements and mystic philosophical concepts.¹ He attempted to bridge the gap between mythological stories of creation and natural philosophical explanations. Though god created the world, he created it the after the likeness of other gods. There is a dilution and gradation in the divine beings and created beings. The Jewish monotheistic worldview is dissimilar to Plato's thought in that a clear distinction between the creation and creatures was maintained (1 Cor 8:6) and humans are the only beings who were created in the image of God (Gen 1:26-28) in the Jewish scriptures.

Substance and Its Predicates

In his work “Substance and Its Predicates,” Aristotle carefully defined the terms and explained the meaning of each term with its distinctions. In his theory of substance, everything exists as a substance in the world. He gave an *a posteriori* explanation of the natural world. He attempted to explain how the names are given to substances, combinations, predications, quantities, and qualifications. If things have a common name and a difference in their being, they are called homonymous. If things have a common name and similarity in being, they are called synonymous. If things have a name from something with a difference in the suffix, they are called paronymous. Some things are always named with combinations, and other things are named without combinations. When someone speaks about something without combination, they always speak of its substance, quantity, qualification, or relative. When someone predicates one thing or another, all things spoken of predicated will be spoken of that thing as well. A substance is called

¹ Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, Plato's Myths, <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/plato-myths/>.

a substance most strictly and primarily when they call something before any prediction. They are called the primary substances (e.g., an individual man or an individual horse). All other things are said of the primary substances. The secondary substances are near the primary substances (e.g., species, genera, etc.). Every substance signifies a specific aspect of "this." He argued that there are perceptible things that exist before perception.

Aristotle provided a helpful framework for defining the terms and associating various substances with their qualifications. His insistence on real substances and their relationship to other predicates clarified the philosophical confusion about reality. His work paved the way for theists, philosophers, and theologians to carefully define their terms with clear distinctions.

Nature and the Four Causes

In his work "Nature and Four Causes," Aristotle made a distinction between the things that exist by nature and the things that exist from other causes. Some things in the world exist by nature, including animals, their parts, plants, and elements like earth, fire, water, etc. These things have a specific nature of their own. Each of these things is a substance. The substances receive accidents, but they also exist without any accidents. For example, wood is the nature of the bed (wood exists by itself before the bed). In his thought, there are two important aspects to the substances: matter and form. The matter is the becoming aspect, and the form is the aspect of the being. There are four types of causes: material, efficient, formal, and final. The material cause involves the thing out of which things come, e.g., the bronze of the statue. The efficient cause is the primary source of change, the formal cause is the essence, and the final cause is the purpose or end for which a thing is done.

Aristotle gave a helpful framework for defining the terms and associating various concepts. His insistence on real substances and their relationship to other accidental properties clarified the philosophical confusion about reality. His *posteriori* thinking helped him to pay careful attention to the created realities in the world. His work helped the natural sciences to define

and distinguish species, genera, families, etc. His work helped philosophers and theologians to clarify their complex philosophical concepts.

Motion

In his work "Motion," Aristotle explained the aspects of motion, its actuality, and agency. First, motion is a change of any kind. Nature involves the principle of motion and alteration. The motion belongs to the continuous class of things. The motion always associates with a substance, quantity, quality, etc. Every mover is moved by something. The fulfillment of the potential is motion. The actuality of potentiality is motion. The process of building from the buildable is a kind of motion. Second, the motion is thought to be indefinite. It is not possible to classify the motion as potentiality or actuality. Some people consider motion as the difference, inequality, or not being. The motion is the fulfillment of the movable as movable. Third, motion is in the movable. The motion is the fulfillment of both the fulfillment of the potentiality and the actuality of the movable. Sometimes, to be acted upon and to act are one and the same respect. For example, it is the same distance between two places. The alteration is the fulfillment of the alterable.

Aristotle's argument and explanation of the motion are valuable in understanding the origins of the universe and life. His explanation of motion helped thinkers and philosophers in relation to the ideas and philosophical concepts in their systems. When Christian thinkers adopted the concept of motion, they applied it to the process of creation and ordered life on the earth and argued for the first mover. Aristotle's explanation of motion, potentiality, and actuality helped Christian thinkers to articulate the doctrines of the trinity, incarnation, and other core theological concepts.

The Unmoved Mover

Aristotle argued that all the things in the world either move or are capable of moving. First, there must be an eternal, unmovable substance. There should be a substance that is eternal and unmovable and distinct from sensible things. There should be an eternal substance whose very

substance itself is actuality. This substance must be without error, eternal, and actual. This eternal and actual substance will move the thing (heaven) that is unceasingly moving. The eternal actual substance moves the other things without being moved. He acknowledged that it is God who is that actual and eternal substance. God is a living being, eternal, and benevolent. Second, the primary mover moves the universe and produces a single and eternal movement. The first unmovable substance also moves the other planets and produces eternal spatial movements. He supposed that the movements of stars and planets were handed down to them from their forefathers as a tradition in the form of myths. He also discussed the problems of the nature of divine thought. One of the problems is how a divine being could continuously think about itself. Third, the nature of the universe consists of good and the highest good. He contemplated the good, order, and connectivity within the world. He concluded that there should be one ruler.

Aristotle examined the philosophical dilemma of the motion within the universe. He acknowledged that there should be an eternal, unmovable mover who moves everything without being moved. He acknowledged that there should be a divine eternal substance that moves everything. However, he did not believe in a personal God who created man to enter into a covenantal relationship with him. However, he gave the appropriate philosophical tools to Christian, Jewish, and Islamic thinkers² to argue for the existence of God based on the eternal movement in creation.

The Ontological Argument

In his ontological argument, Anselm of Canterbury argued that if God exists in thought, he must exist in reality as well. First, he contemplated seeking God. He encouraged people to seek God. He reasoned that humans were created to seek God. He believed that believers put their faith in God so that they may understand him. It is not possible to know God without believing him. God dwells in an approachable light. However, he bestows his grace on people to know him.

² Encyclopedia, Aristotle, <https://www.encyclopedia.com/religion/encyclopedias-almanacs-transcripts-and-maps/aristotledeg>.

Second, even a fool comprehends when he hears about the greater being. When he listens to it, he conceives it. If it exists in his mind, it can also exist in the reality. Therefore, he argued that there exists a being in which nothing greater can be conceived. Third, God cannot be comprehended as not existing. If imagine something not to exist, it is not God. Fourth, a thing can be perceived in two ways. In the first way, when the word suggesting is comprehended, and in the second way when the thing itself is comprehended. God can be not thought to exist in thought and reality. Those who know God cannot think that he cannot exist. God is that than which no greater thing can be conceived. Fifth, God is whatever it is better to exist than not to exist, he is the only creator and self-existing person. Sixth, God is sensible although he is not a body. God is all-powerful, sensible, kind, and passionless.

Anselm's argument is an *a-priori* argument. It is an argument from the cause to the effect. The ontological argument is logical and consistent. It is logically impossible to imagine that "a greater being than which no other greater thing can be conceived" fails to be the greater being in thought and reality. However, such reasoning is circular in nature. It presupposes a prediction and argues back to the same presupposition. It is not helpful to convince the modern secular philosophers.

The Existence of God

In his work "Summa Theologica," Thomas Aquinas argued for the existence of God. In his arguments, first, he discussed the objections and replied to them with sound reasoning. In the first article, he discussed whether the existence of God is self-evident. Some of the objections include natural implantation in mind, ontological argument, and self-evidence of truth. In his replies, he argued for the need for demonstration because of the essence of God, the natural idea is sometimes confused, everyone cannot conceive him in the right way, and the existence of primal reality is not self-evident to humans. In the second article, he discussed the objections if it is possible to demonstrate the existence of God. Some of the objections include faith's nature being dependent on unseen realities, lack of knowledge of God's essence, and deficiency in the

proportion of effects of God from him. He argued that the question of God's existence is a preamble to the articles of faith, before someone thinks about his essence they should demonstrate his existence, and every effect demonstrates its cause. In the third article, he argued for the existence of God based on five pieces of evidence: the necessity of an unmoved mover in the universe, the first cause of everything, the necessary being for all contingent beings, the ultimate good in order for the gradation, the ultimate good and cause of goodness and every other perfection, and the ruler for the governance of the world. In response to the objections, he clarified that God produces good out of evil and that an immovable and self-necessary principle is necessary for the existence of all things.

Aquinas used an a *posteriori* argument for the existence of God. He argued from the effects to the cause. He relied on the work of Aristotle to demonstrate the need for the unmoved mover. Some of his demonstrative arguments are helpful to understand the existence of God. His arguments provide a philosophical foundation for engaging with pluralism, secularism, and polytheism.

The Doctrine of Analogy

In his work "Summa Contra Gentiles," Aquinas argued for divine perfections and his distinction from the creatures. First, he argued that God is universally perfect, he consists of all excellencies, and he exists without a defect. All other beings partake in the while through an imperfect mode. All imperfect beings must be preceded by something perfect. God is the most perfect being. Though God is infinitely perfect, he revealed his glory to Moses. Second, he discussed the likeness of creatures to God. He discussed how the likeness of God is possible and not possible for creatures. He argued that there are some similarity and distinction between creator and creatures. Third, he argued that humans cannot understand what God is by the names that they predicate to him, but only what he is not and how other things are associated with him. Fourth, he argued that divine perfection and the multiplicity of divine designations are not conflicting with divine simplicity. Fifth, one should not equate God with anything in the universe. Sixth, names

should not be given to God and creatures in a purely equivocal way. Sixth, it is possible to use the names of creatures to refer to God's attributes analogically. He also argued that the reality in the names of all good things exists in God before their existence in other beings.

Aquinas maintained the transcendence of God with all his perfections. Since God is perfect and lacks no excellence, humans should not compare him with any creatures who are imperfect. Humans do not know the full depth of God's perfections. All other beings receive their being from him. All humans know about him is what he is not, that is, how he is not like other creatures. He clearly maintained the distinction between creator and creation. His articulation of God's attributes is a philosophical guide for theists and Christian thinkers to know about him and develop their systems of theology.

Ideas

In his work "Ideas," John Locke discussed the ideas in general and they are original. First, the idea is the object of thinking. All ideas originate from a sensation or reflection. These ideas are also noticed in children. The sensations are differently provided in men according to the different substances they converse with. The idea of reflection is perceived after the perception of sensations. The reflections require attention to process the ideas. The soul originates to have ideas when it begins to perceive. The soul thinks but there is no proof for its continual thinking. There are no innate ideas except the ideas that are received from perceptions and reflections. Second, simple ideas are uncompounded appearances. Simple and compound ideas are perceived through the senses. The mind is not capable of producing or demolishing ideas. The second category of ideas is compound ideas which are the result of two or more simple ideas (e.g., comparisons, relations, things, etc.)

Locke is an empiricist who rejected the rationalistic notion of metaphysics. He argued that it is possible to understand human knowledge without the need for innate ideas. His method of understanding reality is based on sense perceptions and reflection. There is no notion of a thinking being. He did not reject the notion of the existence of substances. Locke is right in

understanding the problem of Descartes's rationality. However, his method of pure doubt led to pure empiricism and skepticism.³ He is considered the founder of modern liberal thought.

Of Miracles

In his work "Of Miracles," David Hume provided an inquiry concerning Human understanding. He denied the possibility of miracles and thus rejected the eyewitnesses of miracles and rejected the credibility of the Christian religion. The testimony of the apostles and eyewitnesses to the miracles of the savior is not credible. Because their experience is fallible. A miracle is a violation of the laws of nature. There is much probability of inaccurate and biased witnesses. Therefore, the argument for the lack of miracles is superior. Second, there is no record of the establishment of miracles. No miracle is established in history, attested by authentic men. Since a religionist is always prejudiced, he is more interested in spreading false stories. There is strong evidence against all supernatural and miraculous events. The miracles are only witnessed among common and barbarous people. Many people are ignorant and interested in finding a miracle. Finally, there is no strong evidence for witnesses by a larger number of eyewitnesses. Hume also explained how false religions spread at the beginning of their birth. The intellectuals do not give attention to the new religions. By the time, they consider the religious claims of miracles, the religion already spreads. However, he argued that the foundation for religion is found in faith, not reason.

Hume was a British empiricist. He rejected the notion of rationality. He radicalized the notion of empiricism. He denied the possibility of miracles. He argued that it is not possible to argue for God's existence based on rational evidence. He did not deny the existence of God, but he rejected all supernatural revelation and rational arguments. Thus, he paved the way for theological liberalism and radical skepticism.⁴

³ Rogers, G. A.J., "John Locke." Encyclopedia Britannica, <https://www.britannica.com/biography/John-Locke>.

⁴ Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, David Hume, <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/hume/>.

Pure Reason and the Question of God

In his work “Pure Reason and the Question of God,” Immanuel Kant explained the notions of theoretical and practical cognitions of reason. He argued that it is possible for *a priori* and synthetic ideas to exist. For example, mathematics and physics are *a priori* ideas that are also synthetic. He reasoned that he needs to suspend all knowledge to make room for belief. First, no cognition in us comes before the senses, and with experience, all the reasoning begins. All theoretical sciences of rational consist of *a priori* synthetic judgments as principles including mathematics, natural science, and metaphysics. He explained how the task of metaphysics is possible. The reason is the capacity that provides the principle of cognition *a priori*. He formulated a new concept of transcendental philosophy. The transcendental philosophy is the philosophy of pure and merely speculative reason. It comprises analytic and synthetic cognition *a priori*. There is no place for the principles of morality and its basic concepts. Based on his transcendental reasoning, Kant argued that space and time are not empirical concepts drawn from outer experiences. Instead, it is a necessary presentation as *a priori*. He argued that all the sensibilities are nothing but a disordered presentation of things. He also denied the ontological, cosmological, and theological proofs for the existence of God. Instead, he argued that God is a transcendental reality.

Kant attempted to limit religion and revelation within the bounds of reason. He argued that there are universal imperatives for mankind. However, he denied the original sin and historical existence of Jesus.⁵

Lordship and Bondage

In his work “Lordship and Bondage,” G.W.F. Hegel explored the tension between the lord and the bondsman. In this work, he provided the logical progression of consciousness. In each configuration, consciousness fails to achieve its goal. Thus, it leads to the next configuration of

⁵ Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, Kant’s Philosophy of Religion, <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/kant-religion/>.

consciousness. The goal of consciousness is to achieve self-dependence without the need for the other thing. The two consciousnesses acknowledge the presence of one another. They realize that the means by which they achieve the criteria is by subjugating the other self-consciousness. This arises a new conflict between the other and self-consciousnesses. In this battle, self-consciousness needs to fight to the death for his recognition. The bondman's self-consciousness toiled more and more to produce creatively. Thus, he achieves his self-consciousness. The Lord is enslaved by the work of his slave as he became dependent on his work.

Hegel was sympathetic to religion. He promoted absolute idealism. According to Hegel, humans exist essentially in relation to one another. The slave exists in relation to the master and the master exists in relation to his slave. His ideas influence other philosophers like Karl Marx and theologians like Soren Kierkegaard.⁶

Objective and Subjective Christianity

In his work “Objective and Subjective Christianity,” Soren Kierkegaard argued that faith is primarily a concept of inwardness and subjectivity. Kierkegaard defined a Christian as someone who accepts the dogmas of Christianity. He denied the assumption that everyone who claims to be a Christian in Christendom is not a Christian. The subject matter of Christianity is not determined by the what of Christianity but by the how of the Christian. A person must have appropriate faith in his life. He clarified that a person becomes a Christian not by the objectivity of the doctrine, and subjectivity of the appropriation, but instead by the personal involvement by baptism. He goes further and argues that even the baptism itself is not sufficient to claim himself as a Christian. Though a person baptizes, he still needed to become a Christian. Instead, he argues that a person needs to experience the inward witness of the Spirit.

Kierkegaard expressed his grief over the misconception of people in his time. People are considering themselves Christians but none of them are living a Christian life. Christendom

⁶ Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel, <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/hegel/>.

made people lazy. His disinterest in the formal confession of religion without actual obedience led him to question the objectivity of religion. It led him to propose the subjective obedience and inwardness of religion. He is right in pointing out the problem of external religion. However, his rejection of the objective religion is not grounded in the scriptures. The church is a corporate entity and Christians are expected to live in covenantal relationship with other members of the church.

The Understanding of Other Persons and Their Life-Expressions

In his work “The Understanding of Other Persons and Their Life-Expressions,” Wilhelm Dilthey explained life expressions. Based on experience and self-understanding, humans understand people and their life expressions. First, life expressions are the things that make mental content intelligible for humans. The mode and completion of the understanding vary based on the classes of life expressions. Some of the classes include theoretical, practical, and disclosive. The first class is theoretical which includes concepts, judgments, and complex thought formulations. They communicate the state of affairs, not the state of the intellect. For example, a mathematical formulation is always the same and they do not reveal anything about the speaker. The second class is practical which includes actions. The actions do not intend to communicate but they communicate the intentions of the person. The third class is descriptive which includes the expressions of lived experience. This class of expressions reveals the person who is giving those expressions. These expressions reveal about the person more than he intended to reveal. After explaining the expressions of life, Dilthey explains the modes of understanding. Some of the modes include elementary and higher understanding. The elementary understanding involves the relationship between expression and the content of expression. The higher mode of understanding involves inductive inference. It replaces the sphere of commonality with universality including social, political, economic, and cultural contexts.

Dilthey contributed to the fields of philosophy, hermeneutics, psychology, sociology, etc., He rejected the notions of natural sciences and developed a philosophy of life that conceived man in his historical contingency. He followed the liberal thought of Schleier. He argued that

enlightenment made it problematic to recognize the supernatural aspects of religion. It is possible to feel and think in a religious mood. He considered that religion is not transcendent. For him, religion is merely an experience. The historical accounts of the resurrection and spiritual aspects of religion are challenged. Thus, he undermined the true essence of Christianity.⁷

Theses on Feuerbach

In his work, “Theses on Feuerbach,” Karl Marx criticized the previous materialism and proposed that the essence of humanity is to be understood in his economic and social relations. The defect of previous materialism is that the object and sensuousness are regarded only in the forms of object or perception, but not a sensuous human action. Marx argued that the questions about objectives are practical questions. They should not be limited to theoretical questions. The circumstances always change around us, the educator needs to educate himself. This change of circumstances and corresponding human attitudes is conceived as revolutionary practice. He argued that the secular basis of life needs to be revolutionized in practice. Marx pointed out that Feuerbach did not conceive sensuousness as practical. Marx argued that the essence of man is not an abstraction within individuals. Instead, the essence of man is found in the collaborative of social relationships. The religious belief is a feeling of social product. All communal life is practical. The standpoint of new materialism is the socialized humanity. The task of philosophy should not be limited to interpreting the world. It needs to work towards change in the world.

Marx is an influential thinker who contributed to the fields of philosophy, sociology, and politics. He radicalized the materialistic ideas and argued that the very conception of the human self is the result of historical and material activity. The historical circumstances and the corresponding human attitudes are continuously changing and need to be changed. He understood that religion is a revolt of poor people against their economic struggles. The worship of God is not reasonable. However, it serves the purpose of human spiritual development. Thus, he undermined

⁷ Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, Wilhelm Dilthey, <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/dilthey/>.

a true religion. His influence on politics, social life, and religion is unmistakable. He was successful in influencing many thinkers to embrace Marxism, communism, and socialism.⁸

The Way Back into the Ground of Metaphysics

In his work “The Way Back into the Ground of Metaphysics,” Martin Heidegger explored the concepts of being, phenomenon, and reality. Metaphysics attempts to seek about beings. The truth of being is the essence of metaphysics. The task of metaphysics involves the beings as representatives, but it does not deal with Being itself. To metaphysics, the nature of truth always seems in the derivative form. Though metaphysics cannot speak of Being itself, it continually speaks about the ways of Being. Metaphysics represents beings as beings in their universality and the highest being. It is possible to speak about the location and time of being. The essence of being lies in its existence (being there). The term existence refers to the idea of any reality including God and a grain of sand. Heidegger argued that “that being” exists in man and man alone exists. He explained the meaning of the phrase “man alone exists.” It means that man is that being whose Being is identified by the open standing in the unconcealedness of the Being. All consciousness presupposes the existence of selfhood. The existence of man is the *essentia* of man.

Heidegger formulated his metaphysics based on the conceptions of Augustine, Aristotle, and Kierkegaard. He attempted to explain the concepts of metaphysics in terms of phenomenology and existentialism. He ended up arguing about the end of metaphysics. He supported the German Nazi party. He encouraged methodological atheism in philosophy. For him, God is a philosophical concept. He does not believe in the God of the Bible.

⁸ Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, Marx, <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/marx/>.

The Exemplary Significance of Legal Hermeneutics

In his work “The Exemplary Significance of Legal Hermeneutics,” Hans-Georg Gadamer proposed methods for interpretation in the matters of historical, legal, and theological matters. He argued that there is no gap between human sciences and legal hermeneutics. The legal interpreter constructs the range of applications and derives the meaning. The legal interpreter is not satisfied with the original meaning in the original context. He is also interested in understanding the historical change that has taken place between the original setting and his current setting. Historical understanding is possible only by visualizing the past in its continuity with the present. He acknowledged that scripture is the word of God and it takes precedence over the interpreter. Scripture is the divine declaration of deliverance. The interpretation is not a matter of scientific and academic research. However, the task of interpretation involves a living relationship between the exegetist and the scripture. The interpreter needs to be in relationship with the content of the scriptures. The primary task of the interpreter is application. The interpreter needs to find the true expressed meaning within the text and the hidden meaning in the text. He argued that the task of hermeneutics involves the historically affected consciousness.

Gadamer contributed significantly to the field of hermeneutics. His method is helpful if one uses it with caution. He argued that the task of interpretation involves the combination of history and the present. He is right in understanding the role of the present and the consciousness of the interpreter. The text finds its meaning in the combination of the historical and present setting. In this method, the notion of absolute objectivity of the text is denied. The meaning of the text is dependent upon the historically affected consciousness.⁹

The University Discussion

In his work “The University Discussion,” Antony Flew argued against the possibility of God’s existence. He used the parable of an unseen gardener to reject the notion of God’s existence.

⁹ Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, Hans-Georg Gadamer, <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/gadamer/>.

Two travelers tried to seek the unseen gardener in the jungle. Though they tried to see him, he is not visible. They tried to catch him with the help of an electrified fence and bloodhounds. But they never found him. This leads to the question of the existence of the gardener. It is impossible to make a distinction between the imaginative gardener who was not seen and the non-existence of the gardener. As per the principle of verification, a statement is meaningless unless it is proved or disproved by sense observation. A thing exists only when one examines its existence. He argued that the problem of suffering demands the help of God. He rejected the explanations for the problem of suffering and death. If a God fails to help humans in times of suffering and death, humans should deny the existence of that God. Since there is no real help from God, it is legitimate to question the existence of God. He expressed his disappointment with the believers who are not willing to accept the non-existence of God.

Flew was an influential philosopher. He argued against the existence of God as an atheist. Later, he converted to deism. He believed in the Aristotelian god. He rightly argued the questions to seek the evidence of God. He asked the right questions about why one should believe God if he cannot perceive him and not receive benefits from God. However, he was mistaken in not realizing that he is asking those questions because God created him with the faculties of reasoning. Flew himself did not continue as an atheist because of the strong evidence of the orderliness in the creation.¹⁰

Lectures on Religious Belief

In his work “Lectures on Religious Belief,” Ludwig Wittgenstein discussed the problem of the usage of religious use of the words like the last day, God, and resurrection. He argued that there is no contradiction between the statements “I believe in the last day,” and “I don’t believe in the last day.” The use of the words is different in religion in comparison to science. He contended that one should not attempt to give evidence to prove the faith. The people who claim that

¹⁰ Britannica, Antony-Flew, <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Antony-Flew>.

Christianity has historical proof do not carefully apply the doubt to the historical facts of religion. The ordinary use of the word “belief” is different from its religious use. Wittgenstein examined how people use words differently in different settings. He challenged the problem of using words as if they are self-evident and self-sufficient.

The works of Wittgenstein are difficult to interpret. It seems that he undermined the notions of religion because of the problem of language. Some interpreters understood that he underscored the responsibility of the philosopher in examining the game of language in religion and influence of religious language. He rejected the formal religion. He understood that religion is a way of life and resisted the rational arguments for God’s existence.¹¹ However, he failed to acknowledge the reality of life and truthfulness of the Christianity. God uses language to accomplish his purposes. The very existence of language and its usefulness point out to the God who created the language and made it available to humans.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Allen, Diogenes, and Eric O. Springsted, Eds. *Primary Readings in Philosophy for Understanding Theology*. Westminster John Knox Press, 1997.

Britannica. Entries on Antony Flew and John Locke. <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Antony-Flew/>, <https://www.britannica.com/biography/John-Locke>.

Encyclopedia. Aristotle. <https://www.encyclopedia.com/religion/encyclopedias-almanacs-transcripts-and-maps/aristotledeg>.

Internet Encyclopedia of Philosophy. Ludwig Wittgenstein. <https://iep.utm.edu/wittgens/>

¹¹ Internet Encyclopedia of Philosophy, Ludwig Wittgenstein, <https://iep.utm.edu/wittgens/>.

Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy. Entries on David Hume, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel, Hans-Georg Gadamer, Kant's Philosophy of Religion, Marx, Plato's Myths, and Wilhelm Dilthey. Available at: <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/hume/>, <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/hegel/>, <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/gadamer/>, <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/kant-religion/>, <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/marx/>, <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/plato-myths/>, <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/dilthey/>.